

Physicochemical Studies on Non-stoichiometric Oxides of Yttrium, Praseodymium and Gadolinium. Part-II

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Acidity and excess oxygen of the samples obtained from solid state decomposition of nitrates of yttrium, praseodymium and gadolinium have been determined. Apparent activation energy involved in these processes have also been estimated.

It has been observed that excess oxygen varies exponentially with acidity. Apparent activation energy in case of thermal decomposition of praseodymium nitrate is significantly higher than those of nitrates of yttrium and gadolinium.

RECENTLY considerable work on physical and structural phenomena of non-stoichiometric transition metal oxides has been reported^{1,2}. For the last few years we are studying the electric transport and catalytic activity of non-stoichiometric oxides of rare earth metals obtained from solid state decompositions^{3,4}. Some of them are found to be semiconductor with excellent catalytic capability for chemical decompositions^{5,6}. Though transition metal oxides as a reformation catalyst have been widely studied but it lacks to throw light firstly, on the mechanism of liberation of oxygen in case of rare earth oxide as reformation catalyst and secondly, the surface characterisation which must have bearing on the electronic and catalytic behaviours. Further, the thermogravimetric data besides furnishing valuable information regarding heat treatment processes of the solids, indicate unambiguously about the various stages of physico-chemical changes like dehydration, decomposition *etc* of the solid state decomposition processes.

Keeping this in view, the present investigation was undertaken to measure the physicochemical parameters, like excess oxygen and acidity of non-stoichiometric oxides of yttrium, praseodymium and gadolinium. This paper also deals with the estimation of apparent activation energies of solid state decomposition of nitrates of Y, Pr and Gd.

Experimental

Nitrates of Y, Pr and Gd of 99.99% purity (Indian Rare Earth Ltd.) were used as such.

Preparation of samples and measurements: The non-stoichiometric oxide samples of Y, Pr and Gd at 600, 700, 800 and 960° were prepared by the method as reported earlier⁷. The metal in the oxides was estimated by the usual method. Empirical formulae were derived. The results are shown in Table 1. The acidity measurements were performed by the method of Arora *et al.*⁸ and the results are given

TABLE 1—VALUES OF EXCESS OXYGEN, ACIDITY OF SAMPLES OBTAINED AT DIFFERENT DECOMPOSITION TEMPERATURES

Decomp. temp. °C	Empirical formula	Excess oxygen per 100 g of sample $\times 10^{-2}$	Acidity meq g ⁻¹
600	Y ₂ O _{3.44}	49.4	120.45
700	Y ₂ O _{3.48}	19.0	104.37
800	Y ₂ O _{3.49}	9.5	88.83
960	Y ₂ O _{3.60}	7.6	80.30
600	Pr ₂ O _{3.68}	22.50	32.85
700	Pr ₂ O _{3.99}	15.20	36.50
800	Pr ₂ O _{3.08}	15.20	36.50
960	Pr ₂ O _{3.22}	11.4	29.20
600	Gd ₂ O _{3.5}	17.0	65.70
700	Gd ₂ O _{3.70}	9.5	59.40
800	Gd ₂ O _{3.75}	7.6	47.45
960	Gd ₂ O _{3.20}	6.65	43.8

in Table 1. Measurement of excess oxygen was done by the method described by Volts *et al.*⁹.

Evaluation of activation energy of thermal decomposition: The thermogravimetric study was performed at P and D, F.C.I. Ltd., Sindri using stanton Red-Croft T.G. 750 thermobalance of sensitivity 0.1 mg per division of chart at the heating rate of 10° min⁻¹. The activation energy of solid state thermal decomposition process was evaluated, using the modified equation of Dharwadkar and Phadnis¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

The values of excess oxygen and acidity together with the empirical compositions of the different samples are given in Table 1. Fig. 1 shows how the excess oxygen changes with the change in acidity of the different samples. Fig. 2 is a typical DTG curve of yttrium nitrate.

From Table 1 it appears that except the samples obtained from praseodymium nitrate, acidity values

decrease with rise in decomposition temperature. Similar is the trend of the values of excess oxygen. This observation indicates unambiguously that the

Fig. 1. Plot of acidity vs log (excess oxygen): (O) yttrium oxide, (□) praseodymium oxide and (Δ) gadolinium oxide.

excess oxygen is related with the acidity of the samples somehow or other. The plot of excess oxygen vs acidity (Fig. 1) reveals that the acidity varies exponentially with excess oxygen.

It is also interesting to point out as is obvious from the Table 1 that though the values of acidity of the samples obtained from praseodymium nitrate seem to be more or less the same but they contain considerable amount of excess oxygen, which according to Maxim¹¹ signifies the chemisorbed oxygen. Thus, it is to be concluded that the samples

Fig. 2. DTG curve of $Y(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$.

obtained from praseodymium nitrate would show greater activities for the chemical changes where the excess oxygen plays the key role. The catalytic activity is to be measured to ascertain this.

From the perusal of Table 1 it is obvious that the oxygen content increases regularly with the temperature of decomposition but reverse is the trend of excess oxygen and acidity values. This shows that neither the excess oxygen nor the acidity is at all related to the oxygen content in the samples. Obviously, the catalytic activities of the samples seem to be independent of the oxygen content of the sample. This needs detailed study to corroborate the conclusion.

The study of TGA on nitrates of Y, Pr and Gd was performed. A typical DTG curve of yttrium nitrate is shown in Fig. 2. From a close look it is quite clear that decomposition takes place in four stages in case of yttrium nitrate where as the decomposition takes place in three stages in cases of praseodymium and gadolinium nitrates. Thus, it is to be concluded that the decomposition behaviour of yttrium nitrate is different from that of nitrates of praseodymium. Further, from the DTG curve itself the estimation of different temperatures leading to the formation of stable non-stoichiometric oxides has been done. It appears that the formation of stable oxides from yttrium nitrate and praseodymium nitrate occurs at the same temperature, *i.e.* 480° and that from gadolinium nitrate at 470°. It indicates that in the absence of air stable oxides are formed at the same temperature in these three cases. However, complete dehydration takes place at different temperatures which are 188, 228 and 344° for nitrates of yttrium, praseodymium and gadolinium, respectively. Probably, the half-filled f-orbital present in gadolinium causes the protonisation of water molecules developing force of attraction among the water molecules of crystallisation and nitrates molecules. Consequently, dehydration of gadolinium nitrate takes place at higher temperature as compared to nitrates of yttrium and praseodymium.

Apparent activation energies of solid state decomposition for different stages have been estimated and the results are recorded in the Table 2. The results on activation energy show that the overall value of apparent activation energy in case of decomposition of praseodymium nitrate is considerably higher than that in case of yttrium and gadolinium nitrates. However, the latter two have approximately the same values. It is worthwhile to point out that the activation energy of the reaction is a direct measure of the energy changes involved. Thus, comparatively higher thermal energy is required for the solid state decomposition of praseodymium nitrate, leading to stable oxide product as compared to the decomposition of yttrium and gadolinium nitrates with stable oxide product.

As is clear from Table 2 that the values of activation energies for solid state decomposition

TABLE 2—VALUES OF APPARENT ACTIVATION ENERGY FOR THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF NITRATES OF YTTRIUM, PRASEODYMIUM AND GADOLINIUM

Sl no.	Compd.	First energy of activation E_1 kcal mol ⁻¹	Second energy of activation E_2 kcal mol ⁻¹	Third energy of activation E_3 kcal mol ⁻¹	Total energy of activation E_a kcal mol ⁻¹
1.	Yttrium nitrate	21.740	4.570	13.070	39.380
2.	Praseodymium nitrate	30.077	2.816	26.154	59.047
3.	Gadolinium nitrate	12.205	4.993	19.220	36.418

corresponding to second stage are more or less same in all the three cases. It indicates that probably the second stage is the complete elimination of six molecules of water of crystallisation forming the anhydrous salt and thereafter decomposition starts. Our overall finding on acidity and excess oxygen of these samples is indicative of the exponential relationship between acidity and excess oxygen. Our observation is quite different from that of earlier worker¹². According to him, in case of nickel oxide the acidity varies linearly with excess oxygen. How far, the acidic nature contributes towards the activity of the samples is under study. It is to be mentioned that in case of solid state decomposition of praseodymium nitrate, except the processes of dehydration and decomposition, the diffusion of oxygen predominates causing the greater changes in energy as is obvious from apparent activation energy values.

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